

MONOLITHIC STOKES/DARCY FLUID FORMULATION IN DEFORMABLE MEDIA FOR THE SIMULATION OF RESIN-INFUSION BASED PROCESSES

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes a numerical approach for the simulation of large high-performance composite parts made by infusion processes. Based on a Stokes-Darcy coupling solved by a monolithic approach, this model represents the fluid flows through a non-porous medium and through fibrous preforms assimilated to a porous medium. An updated Lagrangian scheme is used to describe the high deformations undergone by the preforms during the process. The fluid-structure interaction is modelled with an experimental finite large-based behaviour representing the effective influence of preform strain on the medium permeability and therefore on the fluid flow. The resin influence on the preform deformation is modelled by the Terzaghi's law. Based on the resin pressure, this fluid-mechanical coupling introduces a preform swelling during the infusion stage. Finally, this approach is shown to be robust on a complex "T" shape geometry, representative of characteristic industrial difficulties.

1 INTRODUCTION

Liquid Composite Moulding (LCM) processes, such as the Liquid Resin Infusion (LRI) process or Vacuum Assisted RTM (VARTM), are in constant development in high performance applications to propose more efficient ways (cost, cycle times, void content...) to produce large dimension structures. Especially suitable for aeronautics, this process consists in a compaction of a dry reinforcement lay-up preform placed in a half mould sealed by a vacuum bagging film (Figure 1). Under the vacuum depression effect, a liquid resin fills stiff-distribution media placed under/over the preform to create a resin-feeding bed. Then, the resin infuses the layer stack across its stiffness, it swells simultaneously upon the fluid resin pressure effect. When the resin has infused the dry reinforcement, the resin feeding inlet is cut-off and the cure stage begins to freeze the final piece dimensions. Despite numerous advantages, the control of these processes is difficult in terms of final dimensions or filling-time predictions. Today, one of the process comprehension and modelling barrier corresponds to the strong interaction between the reinforcement, *i.e.* the mechanical response, and the resulting fluid flows.

Figure 1: The resin infusion process.

To be representative of the resin distribution flow into the inlet pipelines and specific distribution media (flow media in Figure 1) and through the porous preform, the simulation of these processes needs to consider the

coupling between flows in a porous medium (fibrous reinforcement) and non-porous medium (channels and flow media) while taking into account large mechanical deformations of the porous medium. The objective of this study is to present a robust approach for the simulation of these processes. This model is based on a strongly coupled Stokes-Darcy flow associated with a Lagrangian mechanical formulation considering the large deformation of pre-forms during the process. This numerical model is then applied to the simulation of LRI processes in an industrial framework, characterized by reinforcements with anisotropic properties (permeability and mechanical behaviour), to be representative or predictive of the filling times, the piece dimensions and fibre fraction. Thermal effects and curing reaction of the resin are not considered in this paper.

The fluid/porous-medium flow problem is observed in various domains such as bio-engineering [6], hydrology [15] or industrial processes [10, 11, 18]. A vast literature refers to numerical methods for solving the Stokes-Darcy coupled problem. Some consider a multi-domain or decoupled approach [11, 13, 14] and the others monolithic approach [2, 6, 17, 18]. The decoupled strategy is based on iterative methods to connect the physics in. On the contrary, a monolithic approach consists in using one single mesh to solve both the Stokes and Darcy equations with the same finite element space. This method considers naturally a strong coupling at the Stokes-Darcy interface and the robustness of this approach can be ensured by using specific stabilization techniques [3, 4, 5].

One of the main features of the present study is to couple a unified fluid formulation with a non-linear solid mechanics problem, leading to a robust formulation for the simulation of manufacturing processes in industrial conditions. In the process, mechanical deformations affect significantly the permeability, and consequently the resin flow and filling times. The mechanical fluid/structure or fluid/porous-media interaction is based on the Terzaghi's law [19]. The mechanical deformation, modifying the permeability, is considered through a local modification of the porosity. In such industrial applications, the main difficulties lie in the consideration of real and severe physical properties such as low and anisotropic permeabilities, or thin and complex shapes.

In a first section, the mathematical Stokes-Darcy coupled modelling will be introduced. The mechanical problem and the algorithm to couple the fluid and solid mechanics will be presented in a following section. Finally, numerical simulations of composite manufacturing processes by resin infusion will be exposed.

2 FLUID PROBLEM

2.1 Mathematical model

Let us define the computational domain $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^m$ ($m = 2, 3$), as a bounded domain made up by two non-overlapping sub-domains Ω_s and Ω_d separated by an interface $\Gamma = \partial\Omega_s \cap \partial\Omega_d$ with $\Gamma_{s,D} \cap \Gamma_{s,N} = \emptyset$.

The fluid flow in Ω_s is governed by the Stokes' equations:

$$\begin{aligned} -\nabla \cdot (2\eta\dot{\epsilon}(\mathbf{v}_s)) + \nabla p_s &= \mathbf{f}_s && \text{in } \Omega_s \\ \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}_s &= 0 && \text{in } \Omega_s \\ \mathbf{v}_s &= \mathbf{v}_{s,D} && \text{on } \Gamma_{s,D} \\ \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{n,s} &= -p_{ext,s}\mathbf{n}_s && \text{on } \Gamma_{s,N} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $\dot{\epsilon}$ is the strain rate tensor defined by $\dot{\epsilon}(\mathbf{v}_s) = \frac{1}{2}(\nabla\mathbf{v}_s + \nabla^\top\mathbf{v}_s)$, \mathbf{f}_s is the volumetric force, $\mathbf{v}_{s,D}$ is the velocity imposed on the boundary $\Gamma_{s,D}$, \mathbf{n}_s is the unitary vector normal to the boundary of the domain Ω_s , $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{n,s}$ is the normal stress imposed on $\Gamma_{s,N}$, and η is the fluid viscosity assumed to be Newtonian and constant in time. \mathbf{v}_s and p_s are the fluid velocity and pressure in the Stokes domain whereas ∇ and $\nabla \cdot$ represent the spatial gradient and divergence operators.

The flow of an incompressible fluid through a porous medium Ω_d can be described by the Darcy's equation:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{K}^{-1}\eta\mathbf{v}_d + \nabla p_d &= \mathbf{f}_d && \text{in } \Omega_d \\ \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}_d &= 0 && \text{in } \Omega_d \\ \mathbf{v}_d \cdot \mathbf{n}_d &= \mathbf{v}_{d,D} && \text{on } \Gamma_{d,D} \\ p_d &= p_{ext,d} && \text{on } \Gamma_{d,N} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{K} is the permeability tensor which can be reduced to a scalar in an isotropic case. \mathbf{v}_d is the Darcy's velocity (macroscopic mean velocity), p_d the fluid pressure and $p_{ext,d}$ is the pressure to be prescribed on the boundary

$\Gamma_{d,N}$, \mathbf{n}_d is the unitary vector normal to the boundary of the domain Ω_d and \mathbf{f}_d is a volumetric force.

Between the Stokes and Darcy domains, some specific conditions have to be considered:

1. The mass conservation through the interface Γ is expressed by the continuity of the normal velocity field \mathbf{v} across the interface and writes:

$$\mathbf{v}_s \cdot \mathbf{n}_s + \mathbf{v}_d \cdot \mathbf{n}_d = 0 \quad \text{on } \Gamma \quad (3)$$

2. The continuity of the normal stress is expressed by:

$$\mathbf{n} \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}_s \cdot \mathbf{n} = \mathbf{n} \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}_d \cdot \mathbf{n} \quad \text{on } \Gamma \quad (4)$$

3. The continuity of the tangential velocity is considered through a Beaver Joseph Saffman condition [7] which allow to control the tangential velocity on the interface Γ :

$$2\mathbf{n} \cdot \dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}(\mathbf{v}_s) \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau}_i = -\frac{\alpha}{\sqrt{K_{ii}}}(\mathbf{v}_s \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau}_i) \quad (5)$$

where α is a dimensionless parameter, called slip coefficient, $\boldsymbol{\tau}_i$ ($i = 1, \dots, m-1$) are the unit tangential vectors on the interface and K_{ii} the permeabilities related to the tangential directions.

2.2 Monolithic weak formulation

In this study, the resolution of the fluid problem is based on a monolithic formulation. For this purpose, a consistent mixed (velocity-pressure) formulation is chosen for both Stokes and Darcy problem. The weak formulation of the coupled problem is obtain by summing the weak formulations of each problem and by taking into account the boundary conditions defined above (Equations 3-5). All details concerning the definition of mixed weak formulations for each problem (Stokes and Darcy) can be found in the previous works [1, 2, 3].

Some functional spaces have to be specified to define the monolithic weak formulation of the coupled problem:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{Q}_i &= \mathcal{L}^2(\Omega_i) \\ \mathcal{V}_s &= \{\mathbf{v}_s \in \mathcal{H}^1(\Omega_s) \mid \mathbf{v}_s = \mathbf{v}_{s,D} \text{ on } \Gamma_{s,D}\} \\ \mathcal{W}_s &= \{\mathbf{w}_s \in \mathcal{H}^1(\Omega_s) \mid \mathbf{w}_s = 0 \text{ on } \Gamma_{s,D}\} \\ \mathcal{V}_d &= \{\mathbf{v}_d \in \mathcal{H}(\text{div}, \Omega_d) \mid \mathbf{v}_d = \mathbf{v}_{d,D} \text{ on } \Gamma_{d,D}\} \\ \mathcal{W}_d &= \{\mathbf{w}_d \in \mathcal{H}(\text{div}, \Omega_d) \mid \mathbf{w}_d = 0 \text{ on } \Gamma_{d,D}\} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where $i = s$ on the Stokes' domain and $i = d$ on the Darcy's domain. $\mathcal{L}^2(\Omega_i)$ is the classical Lesbegue space (the square integrable function space), $\mathcal{H}^1(\Omega_i)$ the first Hilbert space and $\mathcal{H}(\text{div})$ the first Hilbert space such that $\mathcal{H}(\text{div}, \Omega_d) = \{\mathbf{v}_d \in \mathcal{L}^2(\Omega_d) \mid \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}_d \in \mathcal{L}^2(\Omega_d)\}$. In these definitions, bold spaces contains vector functions such that each component is in the corresponding scalar function space.

Then, the weak formulation of the monolithic Stokes-Darcy coupled problem consists in finding $[\mathbf{v}, p] \in \mathcal{V} \times \mathcal{Q}$ such that:

$$B_c([\mathbf{v}, p], [\mathbf{w}, q]) = L_c([\mathbf{w}, q]), \quad \forall [\mathbf{w}, q] \text{ defined in } \mathcal{W} \times \mathcal{Q}$$

where $\mathcal{V} = \mathcal{V}_s \times \mathcal{V}_d$, $\mathcal{W} = \mathcal{W}_s \times \mathcal{W}_d$ and $\mathcal{Q} = \mathcal{Q}_s \times \mathcal{Q}_d$. B_c and L_c correspond respectively to the bilinear and linear forms defined by:

$$\begin{aligned} B_c([\mathbf{v}, q], [\mathbf{w}, q]) &= \langle 2\eta \dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}(\mathbf{v}) : \dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}(\mathbf{w}) H_s \rangle_{\Omega} + \langle \frac{\eta}{K} \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{w} H_d \rangle_{\Omega} \\ &\quad - \langle p, \nabla \cdot \mathbf{w} \rangle_{\Omega} + \langle q, \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} \rangle_{\Omega} + \langle \frac{\alpha\eta}{\sqrt{K}} \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{w} \rangle_{\Gamma} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

$$L_c([\mathbf{v}, p], [\mathbf{w}, q]) = \langle \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{w} \rangle_{\Omega} + \langle p_{ext,s} \mathbf{n}, \mathbf{w} \rangle_{\Gamma_{s,N}} + \langle p_{ext,d} \mathbf{n}, \mathbf{w} \rangle_{\Gamma_{d,N}} \quad (8)$$

where \mathbf{f} is defined by \mathbf{f}_i in Ω_i and H_i are Heaviside functions taking the value of 1 in the domain i and 0 elsewhere. For the sake of simplicity, $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$ denotes the scalar product of functions in the \mathcal{L}^2 space.

2.3 Numerical strategy

The computational domain $\Omega \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is discretized into n_{el} non-overlapping elements \mathcal{K} . This yields one single and unstructured mesh made up of triangles in 2D and tetrahedrons in 3D. The finite element discretization is then carried out by restricting the variational formulation to the finite dimensional space $(\mathbf{V}_h \times \mathcal{Q}_h)$ where $\mathbf{V}_h \subset \mathcal{V}$ and $\mathcal{Q}_h \subset \mathcal{Q}$ are the velocity and pressure approximation spaces. In this work, both velocity and pressure fields are approximated by continuous piecewise functions. Stability of the discrete Stokes-Darcy coupled problem is subsequently ensured by using a Variation Multi-Scale (VMS) stabilization method. All details concerning the stabilization technique and the definition of additional stabilization terms can be found in previous works [2, 3, 5, 6].

In the monolithic approach considered in this study, both the interface Γ separating the Stokes and Darcy domain, and Γ_f defining the moving flow front are not described exactly by a set of element. In this approach the interfaces are defined thanks to two level-set functions ϕ et ϕ_f . Level-set techniques consist in defining a signed function distance which represents the distance to the interface (the interface is then represented by the iso-value zero). Applied to moving surfaces, this function change is computed with a convection equation:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \phi_f}{\partial t} + \mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla \phi_f &= 0 \\ \phi_f(x, t = 0) &= \phi_0(x) \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where \mathbf{v} is the fluid velocity provided by the fluid problem solving.

In order to improve the stability and the computation of quantities on interfaces, special integration rules are used in the elements cut by the interfaces [12]. The main idea is to subdivide the elements intercepted by the interfaces into sub-elements but only for integration enrichment purpose. The reconstruction is purely geometric and does not change the number of degree of freedom of the problem (figure 2).

Figure 2: Local reconstruction of an element crossed by an interface Γ defined by a level-set ϕ .

3 MECHANICAL PROBLEM

During the process, preforms undergo finite strains due to a mechanical compaction between both the vacuum bagging and the half mould, and a swelling due to the resin pressure effect. First, this section present the numerical framework used to consider large deformations of the preform and model their non-linear orthotropic behaviour.

3.1 Lagrangian based formulation

The mechanical problem is classically written according to a Lagrangian (Updated) formulation. This formulation is well adapted to represent the non-linear behaviour of the porous medium in a finite strain framework. The Lagrangian problem writes classically as: find $\mathbf{u} \in \mathcal{H}^1$ such as:

$$\int_{\Omega^0} \mathbf{S}(\mathbf{u}) : \dot{\mathbf{E}}(\mathbf{w}) dV - \int_{\partial\Omega_N^0} \mathbf{t} \cdot \mathbf{w} \mathcal{J}_s dS - \int_{\Omega^0} \mathbf{f} \cdot \mathbf{w} \mathcal{J}_v dV = 0, \quad \forall \mathbf{w} \in \mathcal{H}_0^1 \quad (10)$$

where \mathbf{S} is the second Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensor, $\dot{\mathbf{E}}(\mathbf{w})$ is the Green-Lagrange strain tensor rate, \mathbf{f} and \mathbf{t} are respectively the volume force vector and the traction acting respectively on the domain Ω_t (Figure 3). The Lagrangian stress tensor \mathbf{S} can be related to the Cauchy stress tensor $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ with the relations:

$$\mathbf{S} = \mathcal{J}_v \mathbf{F}^{-1} \boldsymbol{\sigma} \mathbf{F}^{-\top} \quad \text{and} \quad \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathcal{J}_v \mathbf{F} \mathbf{S} \mathbf{F}^\top \quad (11)$$

where \mathbf{F} is the gradient tensor associated with the transformation \mathcal{X} (Fig. 3) and defined as:

$$\mathbf{F} = \frac{\partial \mathcal{X}(\mathbf{X}, t)}{\partial \mathbf{X}} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}}{\partial \mathbf{X}} \quad (12)$$

and \mathcal{J}_v is the Jacobian of the transformation defined by $\mathcal{J}_v = \det \mathbf{F} = \frac{dv}{dV}$.

Figure 3: Lagrangian description of the domain motion.

3.2 PREFORM BEHAVIOR

The material considered in this study presents a non-linear behaviour characterized experimentally by a compression test in dry conditions (Figure 4). Considering the mechanical deformations of preforms during the process, the in-plane mechanical properties can generally be considered, as a first approximation, as linear and defined with classical elastic properties. In an orthotropic elastic framework, the material in-plane behaviour can be modelled by:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{S}_{11} \\ \mathbf{S}_{22} \\ \mathbf{S}_{33} \\ \mathbf{S}_{12} \\ \mathbf{S}_{23} \\ \mathbf{S}_{13} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & a_{23} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ a_{31} & a_{32} & a_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & G_{12} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & G_{23} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & G_{13} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{E}_{11} \\ \mathbf{E}_{22} \\ \mathbf{E}_{33} \\ 2\mathbf{E}_{12} \\ 2\mathbf{E}_{23} \\ 2\mathbf{E}_{13} \end{bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

where a_{ij} ($i, j = 1, 2, 3$) are defined by:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} a_{ii} &= E_i \frac{1 - \nu_{jk}\nu_{kj}}{\Delta} \\ a_{ij} &= E_i \frac{\nu_{ij} + \nu_{kj}\nu_{ik}}{\Delta} \end{aligned} \right| \text{with } (k \neq i \neq j, i, j = 1, 2, 3) \quad (14)$$

and where $\Delta = 1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21} - \nu_{23}\nu_{32} - \nu_{31}\nu_{13} - 2\nu_{21}\nu_{32}\nu_{13}$, E_i are the Young moduli in each material direction ν_{ij} are the Poisson coefficients and G_{ij} the shear modulus. As the non-linear transverse behaviour of a fibrous preform is essentially due to local fibre reorganisations, the transverse Poisson ratios are closed to zero and can be approximated by a null value. It allows to represent the transverse behaviour (defined by the transverse direction t) by a relation $S_{tt} = f(E_{tt})$ where f is given by experimental measurements (Figure 4 (a)).

Figure 4: Fibrous preform mechanical transverse behavior (a) and associated permeability evolution (b).

The fluid-structure problem is based on a mutual influence of the resin on the preform behaviour and of the preform strain on its permeability. In this work, the fluid-structure problem is weakly coupled using a sequential algorithm in which each fluid and solid problem is solved considering the last converged results of the other problem. In the solid mechanics problem, the effect of the resin on the preform behaviour is accounted for through a Therzaghi's law [9, 10, 13, 16] :

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{eff} - sp\mathbf{I} \quad (15)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the Cauchy stress tensor in the preform, $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{eff}$ is the effective stress corresponding to the mechanical response of the fibres and $sp\mathbf{I}$ is the hydrostatic fluid pressure. The hydrostatic stress is function of the saturation s of the preform (defined by the Heaviside function $H(\phi_f)$) and of the fluid pressure p . The effect of the mechanical deformation on the fluid flow is taken into account through the local fibre fraction which is one of the main parameters influencing the permeability. Whereas some phenomenological models can be observed in the literature to model the permeability as a function of the porosity, here is considered a permeability evolution (Figure 4 (b)) based on experimental measurements performed in saturated conditions.

4 SIMULATION OF A "T" SHAPE STRINGER

This section is dedicated to the simulation of a stiffened panel usually found in aeronautics and characterized by strong curvatures and thickness variations (Figure 5). The objective of this simulation is to demonstrate the interest of a fluid-solid mechanical coupling for the simulation of LCM processes. The simulation has been performed by using the finite element software Z-set [8, 18]. The computational domain is divided into one purely fluid-domain (flow medium) and three porous domains representing respectively the stringer, the skin and the filler (Figure 5). The dimensions of the geometry are given in Figure 5 and symmetry conditions are used to reduce the size of the numerical model. On this figure, the red dashed line represent the Stokes-Darcy interface. Physical parameters used for the simulation are representative of industrial parameters. The air viscosity is set to $\eta_a = 1.10^{-5} Pa.s$ and the resin viscosity to $\eta_r = 3.10^{-2} Pa.s$. The permeability tensor \mathbf{K} is defined into the structural frame $\mathcal{R} = (0, \mathbf{X}_I, \mathbf{X}_{II})$, where the in plane permeability $K_I = 1.10^{-13} m^2$, and the transverse permeability is initially closed to $K_{II} = 1.10^{-15} m^2$ but evolves with the fibre fraction (Figure 4 (b)). A pressure differential of $1.10^5 Pa$ is prescribed between bottom and top faces of the domain (corresponding respectively to the resin inlet and outlet) whereas the remaining boundaries are considered as impervious walls (fluid boundary conditions in blue Figure 5). Displacements are enforced on the bottom face and a normal stress of $1.10^5 Pa$ is prescribed on the remaining boundaries and represents the atmospheric pressure effect (mechanical boundary conditions in pink Figure 5). As we defined the permeability in the structural frame \mathcal{R} , the mechanical transversally isotropic behaviour law is also defined in \mathcal{R} and corresponds to the behaviour presented in section 3.2. The flow medium mechanical behaviour is modelled as quasi-undeformable, considering an isotropic behaviour defined by a Young modulus of $20 MPa$ and a Poisson coefficient $\nu = 0.3$. For the analysis proposed, the flow medium is initialized filled. The interest of the Stokes-Darcy coupling is then limited but allows to demonstrate the capability of the model to consider sharp variations of mechanical and fluid properties.

Figures 6 (a) and (b) present simulation results after 145 s when only one half of the skin thickness is filled, and then the figures 6(c) and (d) represent results after 562 s when the horizontal part of the stringer is almost filled.

Figure 5: Geometry and boundary conditions used for the simulation of a "T" shape stiffened panel.

Both pressure field and the fiber volume fraction variations between the current deformation state and the initial state (values in accordance with the figure 4) are presented Figure 6 (a). Due to the initial preform compaction under the vacuum depression effect we observe on these figures up to 10% increase in fibre fraction. The figures 6 (b) and (d) show that low permeabilities of the preform introduce a pressure gradient only in the wet area of the porous domain. The evolution of the resin pressure leads to significant modifications in fibre volume fraction according to Figures 6 (a) and (c) due to swelling. Globally the resin pressure introduces an important and non-homogeneous volume fraction changes in the piece leading to non homogeneous permeability in the preform. Considering the relative permeability evolution given in figure 4 (b), a 10% of fibre fraction variation leads to a permeability twice higher or lower modifying significantly the fluid velocity and filling times.

Figure 6: Fiber volume fraction variations (a) (c) and pressure field (b) (d) at the 145 s and 562 s simulation times.

5 CONCLUSION

A numerical strategy has been proposed for the simulation of resin infusion based processes. In these processes, it exists a high interaction between the fluid flow motion and the porous domain deformation. Based on the work of Abouorm & al. for the stabilization of the Stokes-Darcy coupled problem and Celle & al. and then Dereims & al. in an iterative framework, the relevance of a fluid monolithic approach for the coupling to a solid mechanics problem had been demonstrated on the simulation of a "T" shape stiffened panel. Simulation results have shown the robustness of the tools which appeared very stable even on complex simulation case presenting some characteristic difficulties such as strong curvatures, thickness variations but also sharp variations of the mechanical and morphological properties. Simulation results present up to 10% change in fibre fraction in the piece which then affect the permeability and the process significantly. Finally, on the basis of this simulation, the coupling between a fluid and a solid-mechanics problem is essential to be representative of the process fluid velocity, filling times, but also of the final piece dimensions and fibre fractions.

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